

Crosswalking the Dragons

Ontologies and Metadata within the interoperable federated Cultural Heritage Knowledge Graph Ecosystem

Anja Gerber, Florian Thiery

S. Wagner, M. thor Straten, S. Strohm
F. Schenk, D. Stefan, A. Noback, P. Thiery

CAA Int. | 2026 | Mar/Apr 2026 | Vienna | Austria | 02/03/2026

S1: Hic sunt dracones? Link 'em all!

NFDI4Objects

Community Cluster
Semantic Modelling
& Linked Open Data

image created using Google's Gemini

**How to make interdisciplinary Archaeological Research Data FAIR?
Crossy will help us to explore that challenge and treasure!**

The Crossy's try to find a common (infrastructural) language ...

image created using Google's Gemini

Archaeological research relies on federated infrastructures integrating excavation, collection, laboratory, and software data.

Within a federated Knowledge Graph ecosystem, such data can be interlinked using Semantic Web technologies.

Linked Open Data and RDF are the current Method of Choice!

“FAIR Digital Object”

“FAIR Data Object,
exchangeable”

Data

Metadata

PID

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

FDOx – FAIR Data Object, *exchangeable* - A Squirrel Implementation

FDOx - MD.cff / CITATION.cff metadata files

	D1	C0074-148----	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ogham Stone @ UCC Cork, Ireland• KIRI Engine• Anne-Karoline Distel• 10.5281/zenodo.18724635
	D2	CHUIS/1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ogham Stone @ Public Museum Cork, Ireland• KIRI Engine• Florian Thiery• 10.5281/zenodo.18369720
	D3	GOVAN Stone 02 (Hogback)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Govan Stone 02 @ Govan Old Parish Church, UK• Structure from Motion, Agisoft Metashape• Dr Megan Nicole Kasten• https://skfb.ly/6XTQr
	D4	KK013-025----	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• St Lachtain's Well @ Freshford, Ireland• KIRI Engine• Anne-Karoline Distel• https://skfb.ly/oWvIB
	D5	Temporary Cairn	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Temporary Cairn @ Lago di Anterselva, Italy• KIRI Engine• Florian Thiery, Fiona Schenk• 10.5281/zenodo.18732892

FDOx examples in the Cultural Heritage domain - 3D Data

S1	ogham-analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R-based analysis script • CH-Domain: Ogham Stones • Timo Homburg / Florian Thiery
S2	o3d-epidoc-extractor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JAVA-based TEI EpiDoc script • CH-Domain: Ogham Stones • Timo Homburg / Florian Thiery
S3	jupyter-nb-lod	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python-based Jupyter Notebooks • Ogham Stones • Florian Thiery
S4	EPICA-SISAL-FAIRification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python-based analysis / LOD transformation script • Palaeoclimate Data Processing Pipeline • Florian Thiery / Fiona Schenk
S5	campanian-ignimbrite-geo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python-based LOD transformation script • Campanian Ignimbrite (archaeological) findspots • Florian Thiery / Fiona Schenk

FDOx examples in the Cultural Heritage domain - Software

Vanessa Liebler / NFDI4Objects, CC BY-SA 4.0

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) consortium **NFDI4Objects** aims to meet the infrastructural needs of researchers and practitioners who work on the **material remains** of around **2.6 million years** of human and environmental history to develop integrated solutions for FAIR and LOUD data across the humanities and natural sciences.

Central is the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph, which uses CIDOC CRM as a backbone interlinking to community-driven semantic resources such as Wikidata as well as FAIR Digital Objects (FDO).

image created using Google's Gemini

These federated components enable open collaboration, reproducibility, and shared identifiers across institutional and citizen-science boundaries.

- (1) How can heterogeneous metadata be harmonised through ontology-based crosswalks?
- (2) How can collections, software, and analytical data be semantically aligned within federated KGs?
- (3) Which interoperability models sustain reproducible research across disciplines?

Real Objects and [Metadata | Ontologies | Terminologies]

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Metadata Scheme

Ontology Scheme

Florian Thiery & Roman Baum, CC BY 4.0

Florian Thiery & Roman Baum, CC BY 4.0

Terminology Service for for NFDI (TS4NFDI) Scheme

via <https://ts4nfdi.github.io/api-gateway/>

Welcome to TSNFDI API Gateway

The TS4NFDI Federated Service is an advanced, dynamic solution designed to perform federated calls across multiple Terminology Services (TS) within NFDI. It is particularly tailored for environments where integration and aggregation of diverse data sources are essential. The service offers search capabilities, enabling users to refine search results based on specific criteria, and supports responses in both JSON and JSON-LD formats.

Customize your experience by browsing available collections: or creating your own , using only the resources you need across our federated databases:

[agroportal](#) [earthportal](#) [biodyportal](#) [ecportal](#) [lovportal](#) [ebi](#) [tib](#) [zibmed](#) [agrovoc](#) [gnd](#)
[dante](#) [coli-conc](#) [nec](#)

Access the API endpoint for the documentation and usage

Processing and merging data into a unified model based on MOD...

via <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/ts4nfdi>

via <https://ts4nfdi.github.io/api-gateway/>

Collection Details

Provide details about your collection and save it.

Archaeology Test Collection

This is a collection to test TS4NFDI for applications in archaeology.

Make this collection public

ftgeo Select a user...

Available Databases
[dante](#) [coli-conc](#) [tib](#) Select a source...

Available Artefacts Total: 831 artefacts

Selected:

[arbdodat_archaeological_dating](#) [arbdodat_dating_method](#) [arbdodat_site_type](#) [arbdodat_taxonomy](#) [amh_befunde](#) [amh_datierung](#) [amh_material](#) [EVhA](#) [bfo](#) [CRM](#)
[kenom_numismatic_objecttype](#) [nihk_geological_profile_type](#) [nihk_activity_type](#)

Search artefacts... Select All

Collections [Add a Collection](#)

Collection	Description	Tags	Collaborators	Actions
Archaeology Test Collection 0101a77-88e9-482d-ac92-0c81147112a	This is a collection to test TS4NFDI for applications in archaeology.	arbdodat_archaeological_dating (dante) arbdodat_dating_method (dante) arbdodat_site_type (dante) +10 more	ftgeo	Edit Delete
ACTRIS (ACTRIS) 1b7817f0-ea96-4f9c-bca7-023802376644	ACTRIS is the pan-European research infrastructure producing high-quality data and information on...	ACTRIS_CL (earthportal) ACTRIS_VOCAB (earthportal)	admin	Edit Delete
FID Baudigital Project 51941a0-851d-4f6a-8741-ba8f430c4f9d	The FID BAUdigital collection provides a well-selected set of ontologies and controlled...	bau (tib) bdsabi (tib) bk (tib) +23 more	admin	Edit Delete
NFDI4Chem Project 729a569-78d1-4d5c-ba41-904571c84648	The NFDI4Chem Terminology Service is a repository for chemistry and related ontologies providing a...	ifo (tib) lfo (tib) chemief (tib) +41 more	admin	Edit Delete
Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e2249c52-a75f-4f8e-9fa7-6a90828a37c6	Ontologies developed within the German National Research Infrastructure (NFDI).	DFGFO (biodyportal) NFDICORE (biodyportal)	admin	Edit Delete
NFDI4Culture Project 23fa07c2-d503-40d9-9af7-47f06995363c	The NFDI4Culture collection by TIB Terminology Service provides a selection of ontologies for...	bot (tib) cidoc (tib) gesah (tib) +1 more	admin	Edit Delete

How to create an archaeology collection in TS4NFDI?

via <https://terminology.services.base4nfdi.de/api-gateway/search?query=human&showResponseConfiguration=true&collectionId=01fd1a77-88e5-4820-ac92-0fc9b147112a>

via <https://terminology.services.base4nfdi.de/collection/01fd1a77-88e5-4820-ac92-0fc9b147112a>

```
@context": {
  "iri": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/iri",
  "backend_type": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/backend_type",
  "ibase": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/",
  "Synonyms": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#altLabel",
  "created": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/created",
  "hasChildren": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/hasChildren",
  "obsolete": "http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#deprecated",
  "label": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#prefLabel",
  "type": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/source",
  "descriptions": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/description",
  "version": "http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#versionInfo",
  "source_uri": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/source_uri",
  "children": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/children",
  "short_form": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#notation",
  "modified": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/modified",
  "ontology_iri": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/ontology_iri",
  "source_name": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/source_name",
  "ontology": "http://base4nfdi.de/ts4nfdi/schema/ontology"
},
"source_uri": "http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E22",
"children": [],
"short_form": "E22",
"modified": null,
"ontology_iri": "http://bartoc.org/en/node/1644",
"originalResponse": {
  "notation": [
    "E22"
  ]
},
"prefLabel": {
  "en": "Human Made Object"
},
"uri": "http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E22",
"inscheme": [
  {
    "uri": "http://bartoc.org/en/node/1644"
  }
],
"broader": [
  {
    "uri": "http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E19",
    "notation": [
      "E19"
    ]
  }
],
"narrower": [
  null
],
"priority": 197,
"@context": "https://gbv.github.io/jskos/context.json",
"type": [
  "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#Concept"
]
},
"gid": "http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E22",
"source_name": "coli-conc",
"ontology": "1644"
},
}
```

The TS4NFDI Gateway API (still beta version)

image created using Google's Gemini

To combine all worlds we need different types of Crossy

image created using Google's Gemini

We may “split” Crossy into three layers...

Object Core Metadata Profile (OCMDP)

The Object Core Metadata Profile (OCMDP) defines a shared terminology of core metadata elements for NFDI4Objects and aligns them with the emerging NFDI Core Metadata Profile based on DataCite, DCAT, schema.org, and related standards. Technologically, OCMDP is a Crosswalk and curated in a Wikibase-based terminology environment and formalised as a SKOS vocabulary for reuse in services such as TS4NFDI, thereby supporting interoperable metadata creation and integration into the NFDI federated Knowledge Graph.

Material Cultural Heritage Crosswalk Ontology (MaCheCO)

The Material Cultural Heritage Crosswalk Ontology (MaCheCO) provides a crosswalk ontology for aligning domain-specific heritage concepts with CIDOC CRM classes and related semantic frameworks, thereby establishing a shared semantic basis for the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph and its interoperability with other NFDI graphs. Technologically, MaCheCO is curated in Wikibase and formalised as an OWL ontology, enabling the maintenance of crosswalks between, for example, CIDOC CRM, BFO, and NFDI Core, while also supporting publication and reuse through terminology services such as TS4NFDI.

Object Metadata Junction Ontology (OMJO)

The Object Metadata Junction Ontology (OMJO) acts as an interoperability layer that connects the CIDOC CRM-aligned Knowledge Graph of NFDI4Objects with the NFDI Core Metadata Profile derived from DataCite, DCAT, and schema.org. Technologically, OMJO introduces junction entities and linking properties that allow metadata resources to reference and describe domain entities in the CIDOC CRM graph, enabling cross-schema alignment and federated querying across both metadata and domain knowledge layers.

Crossys' NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph Architecture

Examples from OCMDP Crossy

image created using Google's Gemini

A1. Software-related metadata can be modelled using CodeMeta and cross-walked to Citation File Format (CFF), Wikidata, and repository metadata. **FAIR Digital Objects (FDO)** can be also a software research artifact.

via <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>

schema.org. These terms are part of the CodeMeta specification and can be used without any prefix.' Below this is a table with columns: Property, Type, Versions, and Description."/>

Property	Type	Versions	Description
applicationCategory	Text or URL	v2, v3	Type of software application, e.g. 'Game, Multimedia'.
applicationSubCategory	Text or URL	v2, v3	Subcategory of the application, e.g. 'Arcade Game'.
author	Organization or Person	v2, v3	The author of this content or rating. Please note that author is special in that HTML 5 provides a special mechanism for indicating authorship via the rel tag. That is equivalent to this and may be used interchangeably.
citation	CreativeWork or URL	v2, v3	A citation or reference to another creative work, such as another publication, web page, scholarly article, etc.
codeRepository	URL	v2, v3	A link to the repository where the uncompiled, human readable code and related code is located (SVN, GitHub, CodePen, institutional GitLab instance, etc.)
contributor	Organization or Person	v2, v3	A secondary contributor to the CreativeWork or Event.
copyrightHolder	Organization or Person	v2, v3	The party holding the legal copyright to the CreativeWork.
copyrightYear	Number	v1, v3	The year during which the claimed copyright for the CreativeWork was first asserted.
dateCreated	Date	v2, v3	The date on which the CreativeWork was created or the item was added to a Dataset.
dateModified	Date	v2, v3	The date on which the CreativeWork was most recently modified or when the items entry was modified within a Dataset.
datePublished	Date	v2, v3	Date of first broadcast/publication.
description	Text	v2, v3	A description of the item.
downloadUrl	URL	v2, v3	If the file can be downloaded, URL to download the binary.

via <https://citation-file-format.github.io>

What is a CITATION.cff file?

CITATION.cff files are plain text files with human- and machine-readable citation information for software (and datasets). Code developers can include them in their repositories to let others know how to correctly cite their software.

This is an example of a simple CITATION.cff file:

```
cff-version: 1.2.0
message: "If you use this software, please cite it as below."
authors:
  - family-names: Druskat
    given-names: Stephan
  orcid: https://orcid.org/1234-5678-9101-1121
title: "My Research Software"
version: 2.0.4
identifiers:
  - type: doi
    value: 10.5281/zenodo.1234
date-released: 2021-08-11
```

The format of CITATION.cff files is the **Citation File Format (CFF)**.

Supported by GitHub

When you put a CITATION.cff file in the default branch of your GitHub repository, it is automatically linked from the repository landing page, and the citation information is rendered on the repository page, and also provided as BibTeX snippet which users can simply copy! This makes it easy for other users to cite your software project, using the information you've provided. [Read more...](#)

Supported by Zenodo

When you have a CITATION.cff file in your GitHub repository, make a release and publish it on Zenodo via the Zenodo-GitHub integration, Zenodo will use the citation information you've provided to populate the publication entry! This makes it easier for software developers and maintainers to publish their software with complete and correct metadata. [Read the announcement...](#)

Supported by Zotero

When you have a CITATION.cff file in your repository, and someone uses the Zotero browser plugin to import a reference to your repository into their Zotero reference manager, it will use the citation information you've provided to populate the reference entry! This makes it easier for users to get a complete and correct reference to your software, that they can use when they cite your software in their work! [Read the announcement...](#)

CodeMeta and Citation File Format (CFF)

4.1 Basic Metadata

```
# NOTE: FDOx uses https://schema.org/ (with s), not http://schema.org/
Q_BASIC = ""
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX schema: <https://schema.org/>
PREFIX fdo: <https://w3id.org/fdo-squirrel/>
PREFIX codemeta: <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>
```

```
SELECT ?property ?value
WHERE {
  ?fdo a dcat:Dataset .
  VALUES ?prop {
    dct:title
    dct:description
    dct:created
    dct:modified
    dct:issued
    dct:hasVersion
    dct:type
    dct:license
    fdo:context
    schema:funding
    codemeta:programmingLanguage
    codemeta:codeRepository
  }
}
```

property	value
0	codeRepository https://linkedopenogham.github.io/3d-epidoc-e...
1	context Ogham Stones in the Wild and in Museums in Ire...
2	created 2019-08-24
3	description LOD Extractor for TEI/EpiDoc Files from the Og...
4	funding Community Project
5	hasVersion 1.1
6	issued 2020-08-01
7	license https://spdx.org/licenses/MIT.html
8	modified 2024-09-24
9	programmingLanguage JANA
10	programmingLanguage JavaScript
11	title Ogham 3D EpiDoc Extractor
12	type http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147

```
?fdo ?prop ?val .
BIND(REPLACE(STR(?prop), "^.", "")) AS ?property
BIND(STR(?val) AS ?value)
}
ORDER BY ?property
****
```

```
display(Markdown("## 4.1 Basic Metadata"))
display(Markdown("***Software FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_sw, Q_BASIC)
display(Markdown("***3D Model FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_3d, Q_BASIC)
_ = None # suppress Out[] cell output
```

4.6 Keywords / Subjects

```
# Keywords: FDOx uses both dcat:keyword and dct:subject (often duplicated)
# Mix of plain strings and Wikidata URIs
Q_KEYWORDS = ""
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
```

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?keyword ?source
WHERE {
  ?fdo a dcat:Dataset .
  {
    ?fdo dcat:keyword ?keyword . BIND("dcat:keyword" AS ?source)
  } UNION {
    ?fdo dct:subject ?keyword . BIND("dct:subject" AS ?source)
  }
}
```

```
ORDER BY ?source ?keyword
****

display(Markdown("## 4.6 Keywords & Subjects"))
display(Markdown("***Software FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_sw, Q_KEYWORDS)
display(Markdown("***3D Model FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_3d, Q_KEYWORDS)
_ = None # suppress Out[] cell output
```

4.4 Distributions / Files

```
# Distributions: FDOx uses fdo:sha256 (not spdx:checksum) and fdo:path
Q_DIST = ""
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX fdo: <https://w3id.org/fdo-squirrel/>

SELECT ?path ?mediaType ?byteSize ?role ?sha256
WHERE {
  ?fdo a dcat:Dataset .
  ?fdo dcat:distribution ?dist .
  OPTIONAL { ?dist fdo:path ?path }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist dcat:mediaType ?mediaType }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist dcat:byteSize ?byteSize }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist fdo:role ?role }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist fdo:sha256 ?sha256 }
}
```

```
ORDER BY ?role ?path
LIMIT 30
****
```

```
display(Markdown("## 4.4 Distributions (first 30, ordered by role + path)"))
display(Markdown("***Software FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_sw, Q_DIST)
display(Markdown("***3D Model FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_3d, Q_DIST)
_ = None # suppress Out[] cell output
```

	keyword	source
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q18692990	dcat:keyword
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147	dcat:keyword
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q5382396	dcat:keyword
3	EpiDoc	dcat:keyword
4	Linked Open Data	dcat:keyword
5	Ogham Stone	dcat:keyword
6	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q18692990	dct:subject
7	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147	dct:subject
8	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22731	dct:subject
9	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q5382396	dct:subject
10	EpiDoc	dct:subject
11	Linked Open Data	dct:subject
12	Ogham Stone	dct:subject

	path	mediaType	byteSize	role
0	README.md	application/octet-stream	35	documentation
1	words/README.md	application/octet-stream	107	documentation
2	docs/data/oghamireland.js	application/javascript	196296	script
3	docs/js/canvas2svg.js	application/javascript	45180	script
4	docs/js/jsts.js	application/javascript	478060	script
5	docs/js/leaflet-search.js	application/javascript	25672	script
6	docs/js/leaflet.fullscreen.js	application/javascript	5983	script
7	docs/js/leaflet.pattern.js	application/javascript	11197	script
8	docs/js/leaflet.polylineDecorator.js	application/javascript	15929	script
9	docs/js/leaflet_easyprint.js	application/javascript	27586	script
10	docs/js/leaflet_fullscreen.js	application/javascript	2707	script
11	docs/js/leaflet_legend.js	application/javascript	4507	script
12	docs/js/paleocodage.js	application/javascript	39793	script
13	docs/js/proj4.js	application/javascript	71123	script
14	docs/js/querywebworker.js	application/javascript	2	script
15	docs/js/tablesorter.js	application/javascript	40891	script
16	docs/js/turf.min.js	application/javascript	569882	script
17	docs/js/wicket.js	application/javascript	30688	script
18	js/canvas2svg.js	application/javascript	45180	script
19	js/paleocodage.js	application/javascript	39793	script
20	js/tablesorter.js	application/javascript	40891	script
21	src/oghamepidoc/CSVExtractor.java	application/octet-stream	8607	script
22	src/oghamepidoc/EpidocExtractor.java	application/octet-stream	9707	script
23	src/oghamepidoc/Inscription.java	application/octet-stream	52	script
24	src/oghamepidoc/OghamObject.java	application/octet-stream	18078	script
25	src/oghamepidoc/OghamReading.java	application/octet-stream	53	script
26	src/oghamepidoc/OghamSite.java	application/octet-stream	50	script
27	src/oghamepidoc/OghamText.java	application/octet-stream	50	script
28	src/oghamepidoc/OghamUtils.java	application/octet-stream	2084	script
29	src/oghamepidoc/Tuple.java	application/octet-stream	1114	script

Query the FDO Metadata via SPARQL and Jupyter Notebook

Data elements that are usually populated during data entry:

- Object title or name (mandatory)
- Object type or designation (mandatory)
- Classification (recommended)
- Inventory number (mandatory)
- Object description (recommended)
- Materials (recommended)
- Techniques (recommended)
- Measurements (recommended)
- Event in object history [element set] (mandatory)
 - Event type (mandatory)
 - Person/corporate body (conditionally mandatory)
 - Date (conditionally mandatory)
 - Place (conditionally mandatory)
- Subject keyword (recommended)
- Media file [element set] (mandatory)
 - Link to media file (mandatory)
 - Usage rights of media file (mandatory)
 - Rights holder of media file (conditionally mandatory)
 - Alternative text (recommended)

Data fields that are usually populated during or after export from the local database system:

- Record ID (mandatory)
- Record language (mandatory)
- Record type (mandatory)
- Repository of object (mandatory)
- Institution providing record (mandatory)
- Media file: type of media file (mandatory)
- Usage rights of metadata record (mandatory)
- Link to published metadata record (recommended)
- Record date (recommended)

www.minimaldatensatz.de

A2. Museum and Collection data can be modelled using the **Minimum Record Recommendation (MDS v1.1) developed by the Minimum Data Recommendation Working Group. It is LIDO subprofile (XML) and gives recommendations about mandatory and recommended data fields to improve the data quality for museums and collections.**

Object type or designation (mandatory)

```

1 <lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
2   <lido:objectWorkType>
3     <lido:conceptID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00099">http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300199921</lido:conceptID>
4     <lido:term xml:lang="de">Brotmesser</lido:term>
5     <lido:term xml:lang="en">bread knives</lido:term>
6   </lido:objectWorkType>
7 </lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>

```

Expression in LIDO v1.1

```

1 <lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
2   <lido:objectWorkType>
3     <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300199921">
4       <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Brotmesser</skos:prefLabel>
5       <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">bread knives</skos:prefLabel>
6     </skos:Concept>
7   </lido:objectWorkType>
8 </lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>

```

Comparison with relevant standards and database models

Standard	Element name
German Digital Library: Metadata requirements for data provision	Objekttyp
German Digital Library LIDO application profile (DDB-LIDO)	<objectWorkType>
CCC-LIDO Application profile	Objekt type <objectWorkType>
DFG Basic Data Record	Source Object Type
DFG Practical Guidelines on Digitisation : LIDO core metadata	Object or work type <objectWorkType>
Europeana Data Model (EDM)	<dc:type>

Screenshot from the Minimum Record Recommendation for the data field "Object type".

Screenshot from the Mapping of the OCDMP to [schema.org](#) (work in progress)

notation	prefLabel	prefLabel_en	schema.org
>> Terms (Minimaldatensatzempfehlung)			
NPIU6Z	Objekttitel oder -benennung	Object title or name	name
N7GSJC	Objekttyp oder -bezeichnung	Object type or designation	subjectOf
AG90KQ	Klassifikation	Classification	keywords
FYX7BJ	Inventarnummer	Inventory number	sameAs
O83VQV	Objektbeschreibung	Object description	description
NXSHOZ	Material	Materials	material
L4QL7A	Technik	Techniques	
NZ1LIC	Maße	Measurements	size
II4KBR	Ereignistyp	Event type	event
W4Q54V	Person/Körperschaft	Person/corporate body	creator
VMOC3V	Datierung	Date	dateModified, temporalCoverage, dateCreated
J7B6IT	Ort	Place	spatialCoverage, locationCreated
XRFX8T	Inhaltsschlagwort	Subject keyword	keywords
IN8FTA	Link zur Mediendatei	Link to media file	distribution, url
J7BFQ1	Nutzungsrechte Mediendatei	Usage rights of media file	usageInfo, license, conditionsOfAccess
W6IBZZ	Rechtswahrnehmung Mediendatei	Rights holder of media file	copyrightHolder, publishingPrinciples
TY837W	Alternativtext	Alternative text	text
U2H4FS	ID Datensatz	Record ID	identifier
PS17P1	Sprache des Datensatzes	Record language	language
SUC0KE	Datensatzart	Record type	distribution.encodingFormat
WF8UZW	Verwahrende Einrichtung	Repository of object	contributor
NFD00M	Datensatzerstellende Einrichtung	Institution providing record	publisher, producer
MYRFBI	Mediendatei: Medientyp	Media file: type of media file	fileFormat
SL5IM1	Nutzungsrechte Metadaten	Usage rights of metadata record	usageInfo, license
HXKTF8	Link zum veröffentlichten Metadatenatz	Link to published metadata record	contentURL
QH2X8P	Datierung des Datensatzes	Record date	copyrightYear

The collection-level metadata can be expressed as RDF entities and harmonised with DCAT and CIDOC CRM concepts, enabling inter-repository querying within the NFDI ecosystem.

image created using Google's Gemini

Examples from MaCheCO Crossy

Screenshot from the WissKI VRU, maintained and developed by FAU Erlangen-Nuremberg, <https://nfdi4objects.wisski.data.fau.de/>,

Screenshot of the classes in the Objects Ontology for the object biographies, Sarah Wagner, FAU Erlangen-Nuremberg

E1	-	-	-	-	-	CRM Entity
E2	-	-	-	-	-	Temporal Entity
E3	-	-	-	-	-	Condition State
E4	-	-	-	-	-	Period
E5	-	-	-	-	-	Event
E7	-	-	-	-	-	Museum_or_Collection_Affiliation
	-	-	-	-	-	Activity
	-	-	-	-	-	Commissioning
	-	-	-	-	-	Cultural_Activity
	-	-	-	-	-	Encounter_Event (also Subclass of S19 CRM Sci)
	-	-	-	-	-	Excavation (also Subclass of A9 CRM Archaeo)
	-	-	-	-	-	Object_Documentation
	-	-	-	-	-	Reception
	-	-	-	-	-	Research Activity
	-	-	-	-	-	Usage
E8	-	-	-	-	-	Acquisition
E9	-	-	-	-	-	Move
	-	-	-	-	-	Movement_from
	-	-	-	-	-	Movement_to
E10	-	-	-	-	-	Transfer of Custody
	-	-	-	-	-	Accession
	-	-	-	-	-	Deaccession
	-	-	-	-	-	Receivment_of_Custody
	-	-	-	-	-	Surrender_of_Custody
E11	-	-	-	-	-	Modification
E12	-	-	-	-	-	Production
E79	-	-	-	-	-	Part Addition
E80	-	-	-	-	-	Part Removal
E13	-	-	-	-	-	Attribute Assignment
	-	-	-	-	-	Actor_Assignment
	-	-	-	-	-	Appellation_Assignment
	-	-	-	-	-	Design_or_Procedure_Assignment
	-	-	-	-	-	Editing
	-	-	-	-	-	Iconography_Assignment
	-	-	-	-	-	Material_Assignment
	-	-	-	-	-	Place_Assignment
	-	-	-	-	-	Time_Assignment
E14	-	-	-	-	-	Condition Assessment

B1. Within the object-biograph, excavation, collection, conservation, and analytical events are modelled as CIDOC CRM instances, forming a coherent lifecycle representation of artefacts.

+	Herstellung	Group [nfdi4objects:Source → crm:P108i_was_produced_by → crm:E12_Production]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>Hersteller (Person)</i>	nfdi4objects:Source → crm:P108i_was_produced_by → crm:E12_Production → crm:P14_carried_out_by → crm:E21_Person → crm:P1_is_identified_by → crm:E41_Appellation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) 1	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>Hersteller (Körperschaft)</i>	nfdi4objects:Source → crm:P108i_was_produced_by → crm:E12_Production → crm:P14_carried_out_by → nfdi4objects:Corporate_Body → crm:P1_is_identified_by → crm:E41_Appellation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>Datum</i>	nfdi4objects:Source → crm:P108i_was_produced_by → crm:E12_Production → crm:P4_has_time-span → crm:E52_Time-Span	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Entity reference 1	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>Ort</i>	nfdi4objects:Source → crm:P108i_was_produced_by → crm:E12_Production → crm:P7_took_place_at → nfdi4objects:Geographical_Place → crm:P1_is_identified_by → crm:E41_Appellation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>verwaltende Institution</i>	nfdi4objects:Source → crm:P49_has_former_or_current_keeper → nfdi4objects:Corporate_Body → crm:P1_is_identified_by → crm:E41_Appellation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) 1	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>URL</i>	nfdi4objects:Source → crm:P1_is_identified_by → nfdi4objects:URL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Link Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	Quelleninhalt	Group [nfdi4objects:Source_Content]	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>ID</i>	nfdi4objects:Source_Content → crm:P48_has_preferred_identifier → nfdi4objects:Identifier	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) 1	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>Titel</i>	nfdi4objects:Source_Content → crm:P102_has_title → crm:E35_Title	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾
+	<i>Art des Quelleninhalts</i>	nfdi4objects:Source_Content → crm:P2_has_type → nfdi4objects:Source_Content_Type → crm:P1_is_identified_by → crm:E41_Appellation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Text (plain) Unlimited	<input type="text" value="Edit"/> ▾

Screenshot of the WissKI Pathbuilder, FAU Erlangen-Nuremberg

Implemented within a [WissKI-based KG](#) prototype, this model demonstrates, how provenance and transformation processes can be linked to OCM DP modules.

This is an online editor for Lido-to-RDF mappings (x3ml). Mapping rules are editable in the left section. Two text fields for applying the rules are shown on the right.

The top-right field shows the result of the mapping for the source data shown underneath. [imprint](#) | [contact](#) | [barrier-free](#)

Mappings (x3ml):

[Add mapping](#) [Clear all](#) [Load default](#) [Upload](#) [Download](#)

Mapping 1 from: "://lido:lido"

Mapping 2 from: "lido:actor"

Path:

lido:actor

Entity:

crm:E21_Person

[Conditions](#) [Add Link](#) [Delete](#)

Skip

Link 2-1 to: "lido:actorID"

Link 2-2 to: "lido:nameActorSet/lido:appellationValue"

Link 2-3 to: "lido:nameActorSet/lido:sourceAppellation"

Link 2-4 to: "lido:nationalityActor"

Link 2-5 to: "lido:vitalDatesActor/lido:earliestDate"

Link 2-6 to: "lido:vitalDatesActor/lido:earliestDate"

Link 2-7 to: "lido:vitalDatesActor/lido:latestDate"

Link 2-8 to: "lido:vitalDatesActor/lido:latestDate"

Link 2-9 to: "lido:vitalDatesActor/lido:earliestDate"

[Apply mappings](#) output format: n3

Use BNodes

```
1 @prefix crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/> .
2 @prefix lido_term: <http://terminology.lido-schema.org/> .
3 @prefix n4o: <http://graph.nfdi4objects.net/lido/> .
4 @prefix ns1: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P91_has_unit/skos:Concept/skos: > .
5 @prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
6
7 n4o:02fbc7a6edaf1ad6f67d43e431bd1e5d a crm:E39_Actor ;
8   crm:P131_is_identified_by "Museum für Kunst und Gewerbe"@de ;
9   crm:P48_has_preferred_identifier <https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/organisations/DE-MUS-059918> .
10
11 n4o:0b76bd2d4e8ab18b3f11a74df838d20 a crm:E31_Document ;
12   crm:P104_is_subject_to _lfd104f203cddcf8b2c7870a02ebbc1 ;
13   crm:P105_right_held_by _153704f8b2f0ab0b1c30099b418b057b,
14     _5bde05759a43b232ad4967075cab53 ;
15   crm:P2_has_type lido_term:lido00100 ;
16   crm:P48_has_preferred_identifier "dc00018494" .
17
18 n4o:0b0719466cf8b996c9caabf20dcd37d a crm:E22_Man-Made_Object ;
19   crm:P1081_was_produced_by [ a crm:E11_Modification,
20     crm:E12_Production,
21     crm:E7_Activity ;
22     crm:P14_carried_out_by n4o:1d8c91b4ef27e2a379b98668b050ef6a,
23     n4o:rd5d360b72543cd4f11740883f254a8c,
24     n4o:ee802ee9f37575d2a08993d0a1b20d ;
25     crm:P2_has_type [ a crm:E55_Type ] ;
26     crm:P3_has_note [ a rdfs:Literal,
27       [ a rdfs:Literal ],
28       [ a rdfs:Literal ],
29       "um 1600" ] ;
30     crm:P45_consists_of <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300011857>,
31       <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300053029>,
32       <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300375333>,
33       <https://d-nb.info/gnd/7697258-6>,
34       "Ebenholz"@de,
35       "Eisenstein (Material)"@de .
36
```

Screenshot of the NFDI4Objects LIDO2RDF mapper (X3ML), VZG, Josef Heers, graph.nfdi4objects.net/tools, mapping work in progress within the german LIDO WG.

Source (lido/xml): [Upload](#) [Default](#)

```
1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2 <!-- lido xmlns:x3ml="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" xmlns="http://www.lido-schema.org" xmlns:owl="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#" xmlns:r:
3 <lido:lidoReID lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00100">DE-MUS-059918/dc00018494</lido:lidoReID>
4 <lido:descriptiveMetadata xml:lang="de">
5 <lido:objectClassificationWrap>
6 <lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
7 <lido:objectWorkType>
8 <skos:Concept rdf:about="http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300038888">
9 <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="de">Kabinettschrank</skos:prefLabel>
10 <skos:prefLabel xml:lang="en">cabinets (case furniture)</skos:prefLabel>
11 <skos:exactMatch>http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300379868</skos:exactMatch>
12 </skos:Concept>
13 </lido:objectWorkType>
14 </lido:objectWorkTypeWrap>
15 <lido:classificationWrap>
16 <lido:classification lido:type="http://terminology.lido-schema.org/lido00053">
17 <skos:Concept rdf:about="https://d-nb.info/gnd/4039860-2">
```

B2. The LIDO-to-CIDOC CRM mapping establishes correspondences between LIDO elements and CRM classes, enabling museums and archives to publish interoperable RDF data directly consumable by the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

A PROSOPOGRAPHICAL DATABASE

Prosopographia Memphitica

The database includes all identified persons attested for the royal residence and national centre Memphis during the New Kingdom (1539–1077 BC) as well as their documented official titles and the inscribed objects and monuments on which they are attested.

Explore the database and filter by

-
 PERSONS
-
 OBJECTS
-
 TITLES

Mapping a dataset of the Prosopographia Memphitica in CIDOC CRM, Anja Gerber, Andreas Frech as preparation for LIDO for archaeology and also for LIDO2RDF

<https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/sparql>

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL Collections Terminologies Mappings Tools Manual

SPARQL endpoint /api/sparql1 (see documentation) Example queries:

```

1 - PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
2 PREFIX nfdi: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT * WHERE {
4   ?sub ?pred ?obj .
5 } LIMIT 10
  
```

Table Response 16 results Simple view Ellipse Filter query results Page size: 50 repository

collection	name
1 n40c:2	Paläontologischen Sammlung der FAU Geowissenschaftliche Sammlung der FAU
2 n40c:1	Ur- und Frühgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU
3 n40c:6	Schulgeschichtliche Sammlung der FAU und Schulmuseum
4 n40c:5	Medizinische Sammlung der FAU
5 n40c:3	Graphische Sammlung der FAU
6 n40c:4	Musikinstrumentensammlung der FAU
7 n40c:14	Kommentierte Online-Edition der fünf Reisetagebücher Hans Poses (1939 -1942)
8 n40c:15	Corpus Vitrearum Medii Aevi Deutschland
9 n40c:7	KENOM Virtuelles Münzportal (via LIDO)
10 n40c:8	Samian Research Database
11 n40c:9	Linked Open Ogham
12 n40c:10	African Red Slip Ware
13 n40c:11	Digitale Sammlungen der Museen der Klassikstiftung Weimar
14 n40c:12	Graphische Sammlung des Germanisches Nationalmuseums
15 n40c:13	KENOM (via Nomisma)
16 n40c:16	Berliner Kunstammer

LIDO and CIDOC CRM for the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

- Anthropological Data
- Archaeobotanical Data
- Archaeozoological Data

CIDOC CRM
N4O ObjectOntology

KGI4.nfdi
Knowledge Graph Infrastructure
for the German National Research
Data Infrastructure

- Physical Thing
 - Physical Feature
 - Physical Human-Made Thing
 - Curated Holding
 - Human-Made Feature
 - Human-Made Object
- Physical Object
 - Biological Object
 - Human-Made Object

- OWL Thing
 - Resource (rdfs:Resource)
 - PROV-O Entity
 - Thing
 - BFO entity
 - E1 CRM Entität
 - aDNA sample relation
 - E2 Temporal Entity
 - E52 Time-Span
 - E77 Persistent Item
 - E92 Spacetime Volume
 - No Information About Entity
 - PATO quality
 - Pleiades Place
 - E53 Place
 - GeoSPARQL Spatial Object
 - GeoSPARQL Feature
 - GeoSPARQL Geometry
 - SF Geometry
 - SF Point
 - Pleiades Location
 - Discovery Site
 - LADO Location
 - LADO Discovery Site
 - LADO Kiln Region
 - LADO Production Centre
 - LADO Repository Location
 - Site
 - LADO Place as a Concept
 - Country
 - Place
 - TIME Temporal Entity

The ArNO ontology intertwines different ontologies to allow a CIDOC CRM-based modelling of archaeo-natural data, currently ancient DNA data from the Poseidon framework.

B3a. The Archaeo-Natural Ontology (ArNO) will integrate archaeo-natural datasets, e.g., from the Poseidon archives.

via <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/GeoScience-FAIRification-LOD>

B3b. GeoScience-FAIRification-LOD: Palaeoclimate Data Processing Pipeline

Grotte de Villars

- Grotte de Villars, Frankreich
- OSM: [node/2423303117](https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/2423303117)
- Wikidata: [Q177657](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q177657)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: Grotte de Villars (2423303117)

Version #6

POI+routes Dordogne

Bearbeitet vor über 1 Jahr von Coucouf

Änderungssatz #153778320

Standort: 45.4425621, 0.7853010

Tags

| | |
|---------------------|---|
| alt_name | Grotte Préhistorique du Cluzeau |
| fee | yes |
| heritage | 2 |
| heritage:operator | mhs |
| mhsinscription_date | 1958-12-09 |
| name | Grotte de Villars |
| natural | cave_entrance |
| ref:mhs | PA00083067 |
| source:heritage | data.gouv.fr, Ministère de la Culture - 2016 |
| tourism | attraction |
| website | http://grotte-villars.com |
| wikidata | Q177657 |
| wikipedia | fr:Grotte de Villars |

↑ © Grotte de Villars, via <https://grotte-villars.com/en/the-villars-cave/>

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL·E

Develop an ontology based on classes and properties of Wikidata, mapped to CIDOC CRM to ensure semantic alignment and interoperability

B4a. Data from Wikidata and other Wikibases are integrated into the MaCheCO ontology through semi-automated RDF pipelines

Fiachre's Well

- Saint Fiachre's Well, Freshford
- OSM: [node/8515265450](#)
- Wikidata: [Q121842432](#)
- SMR: [KK020-050004](#)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: Saint
Fiachre's Well
(8515265450)

Version #9

refl:Esmr requires heritage=2

Bearbeitet vor über 1 Jahr von geozeisig

Änderungssatz #160155386

Standort: 52.6216672, -7.1978959

Tags

| | |
|------------------------|--|
| description | In a hollow, sheltered by an outcrop of natural rock. Steps leading into the underground chamber. Access via driveway into Sheastown House from R700 on the last Sunday in August around 3pm and the 9 days before in the evening during the novena. |
| heritage | 2 |
| heritage:operator | I:Esmr |
| name | Saint Fiachre's Well |
| name:etymologywikidata | Q953927 |
| natural | spring |
| place_of_worship | holy_well |
| refl:Esmr | KK020-050004 |
| service_times | Aug Su[-1] |
| source | British war office map:SMR:survey |
| subject:wikidata | Q953927 |
| survey:date | 2023-08-25 |
| url:sketchfab | https://skfb.ly/pq67u |
| wikidata | Q121842432 |
| wikimedia_commons | Category:St Fiachra's Well, Sheastown |

↑ Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

↑ b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWwIB>

Stefan, D., Thiery, F., & Schenk, F. (2025). How do we integrate community data from Wikidata and the fuzzy-sl Wikibase into a cultural heritage knowledge graph?. CAA 2025 - Digital Horizons: Embracing heritage in an evolving world (CAA 2025), Athens, Greece. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17338461>

1. create CIDOC-Classes
2. create sub-classes of these in instances of Wikibase items

E26 Physical Feature (Q134301386)

Item Discussion

This class comprises identifiable features that are physically attached in an integral way to particular physical objects. Features share many of the attributes of instances of E19 Physical Object.
 crm:E26_Physical_Feature

• In more languages

Statements

| | | |
|------------------|---|----------------|
| subclass of | CIDOC-CRM Class | - 0 references |
| equivalent class | http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E26_Physical_Feature | - 0 references |

https://cidoc-crm.org/html/cidoc_crm_v7.1.3.html#E25

E25 Human-Made Feature (Q134301417)

Item Discussion

This class comprises physical features that are purposely created by human activity, such as scratches, etc. In particular, it includes the information encoding features on mechanical or digital carriers.
 crm:E25_Human-Made_Feature

• In more languages

Statements

| | | |
|------------------|---|----------------|
| subclass of | CIDOC-CRM Class | - 0 references |
| equivalent class | http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E25_Human-Made_Feature | - 0 references |

E26 Physical Feature (Q147)

This class comprises identifiable features that are physically attached in an integral way to particular physical objects. Features share many of the attributes of instances of E19 Physical Object.
 crm:E26_Physical_Feature

• In more languages

Statements

| | | |
|------------------|---|----------------|
| subclass of | CIDOC-CRM Class | - 0 references |
| equivalent class | http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E26_Physical_Feature | - 0 references |

https://cidoc-crm.org/html/cidoc_crm_v7.1.3.html#E53

E53 Place (Q146)

This class comprises extents in the natural space where people live, in particular on the surface of the Earth, in the pure sense of physics: independent from temporal phenomena and matter. They may serve describing the physical location of things or phenomena or other areas of interest.
 crm:E53_Place

• In more languages

Statements

| | | | |
|------------------|---|----------------|---------------------------------|
| subclass of | CIDOC-CRM Class | - 0 references | edit |
| | | | + add reference |
| | | | + add value |
| equivalent class | http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/E53_Place | - 0 references | edit |

https://cidoc-crm.org/html/cidoc_crm_v7.1.3.html#E26

Human interaction in Wikibases

Saint Fiachra's Well (Q121842432)

Item Discussion

holy well in the townland of Sheestown/ Sheestown, Co. Kilkenny
St. Fiachra's Well | St Fiachra's Well | St. Fiacre's Well

instance of

holy well

3 references

Holy Well Semantic Concept

0 references

holy well

state of use in use

point in time 2023

1 reference

stated in survey

architectural structure

0 references

holy well (Q1371047)

Item Discussion

spring or other small body of water revered either i
sacred spring

subclass of

fountain

0 references

structure of worship

0 references

spring

0 references

water well

0 references

E26 Physical Feature

0 references

architectural structure (Q811979)

Item Discussion

human-designed and -made structure

subclass of

artificial physical structure

0 references

fixed construction

0 references

work

0 references

E25 Human-Made Feature

0 references

Wikibase examples

B4b. Data from OpenStreetMap are integrated into the MaCheCO ontology through semi-automated RDF pipelines.

CIIC 178

- Coumeenole North / Dunmore Head
- OSM: [node/5145413640](#)
- Wikidata: [Q70892682](#)
- SMR: KE052-059002-

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: CIIC 178
(5145413640)

Version #10

ref:IEsmr requires heritage=2

Bearbeitet vor über 1 Jahr von geozeisig
Änderungssatz #159661420
Standort: 52.1102541, -10.4731829

Tags

| | |
|-------------------|--|
| heritage | 2 |
| heritage:operator | IEsmr |
| historic | ogham_stone |
| inscription | ERC MAQI MAQI-
ERCIAS MU DOVINIA |
| moved | no |
| name | CIIC 178 |
| project | ogham.link |
| ref:IEsmr | KE052-059002- |
| source | survey |
| wikidata | Q70892682 |
| wikimedia_commons | File:Coumeenole_Og
ham_Stone_(Dunmore
_Head).jpg |

↑ Ogham in 3D Project, DIAS,
CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

Albert Bridge

- Albert Bridge, Glasgow
- OSM: [node/12923704831](#)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten:
12923704831

Version #2

Edit Survey point.

Bearbeitet vor 9 Monaten von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #167794702
Standort: 55.8527993, -4.2472940

Tags

| | |
|-----------------------|-------------------------------------|
| benchmark | yes |
| man_made | survey_point |
| surveydate | 2025-06-18 |
| survey_pointstructure | cut |
| wikimedia_commons | File:Benchmark on Albert Bridge.jpg |

↑ Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

OSM to LOD - Example Ordnance Survey Benchmark at Albert Bridge, Glasgow

B5. Using the Fuzzy Spatial Locations Ontology (FSL-O), and the fuzzy-sl Wikibase spatial fuzzyness can be linked to CIDOC CRM

Modelling Scheme of the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

Florian Thiery & Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0

Campanian Ignimbrite tephra findspots are E53 Place

Franchthi Cave

- Franchthi Cave, Griechenland
- OSM: [node/1221172611](#)
- Wikidata: [Q1441331](#)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

↑ Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

↑ Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Knoten: Franchthi Cave (1221172611)

Version #8

(kein Kommentar)

Bearbeitet vor etwa 2 Monaten von NikosSkouteris

Änderungssatz #178017325

Standort: 37,4224939, 23,1311197

Tags

| | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------------------|
| archaeological_site | settlement |
| historic | archaeological_site |
| historic:civilization | prehistoric |
| name | Σπήλαιο Φράχθι |
| name:en | Franchthi Cave |
| wikidata | Q1441331 |
| wikipedia | en:Franchthi Cave |

↑ © Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

Franchthi Cave (Greece) EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_45

The Franchthi Cave (Greece) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

| Property | Value |
|--|---|
| <code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsl:certaintyDesc) | findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en) |
| <code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsl:certaintyLevel) | high (fsl:high) [x] |
| <code>hasReference</code> (fsl:hasReference) | Fedele et al., 2003 (xsd:string) |
| <code>partOf</code> (fsl:partOf) | CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x] |
| <code>siteType</code> (fsl:siteType) | ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] |
| <code>spatialType</code> (fsl:spatialType) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsl:Cave) [x] |
| <code>hasGeometry</code> (gsp:hasGeometry) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cisite_45_geom (fsl:cisite_45_geom) |
| <code>type</code> (rdf:type) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (placodes:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x] |
| <code>comment</code> (rdfs:comment) | CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en) |
| <code>label</code> (rdfs:label) | Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en) |
| <code>closeMatch</code> (skos:closeMatch) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 122172811 (122172811) [x] Q1444331 (wikidata:Q1444331) [x] |
| <code>prefLabel</code> (skos:prefLabel) | Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en) |
| <code>scopeNote</code> (skos:scopeNote) | CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en) |
| <code>is member</code> (rdfs:member) of | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place instances collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site instances collection (fsl:Site_collection) |
| <code>is used</code> (prov:used) of | cisite_45_activity (fsl:cisite_45_activity) |

Franchthi Cave (Q111)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

+ 31 more languages

View changes

Franchthi page

Help about Wikidata

Language **Label** **Description** **Also known as**

| | | | |
|-----------------|------------------|-------------------------------|--|
| British English | No label defined | No description defined | |
| English | Franchthi Cave | Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot | |

Statements

Instance of

- Geological Site
- 0 references
- Archaeological Site
- 0 references

part of

- Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
- 0 references

has spatial type

- Cave
- 0 references

has reference

- Fedele et al., 2003
- 0 references

has spatial category

- Archaeology
- 0 references
- Geology
- 0 references

has coordinate

- 37°29'21.47N, 23°7'52.07E
- certainty level: High
- entity description: findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap
- method used: GeoPubby
- writing person: Fuzzy-Schem
- instance type (wikibase): Textual Description
- source type (wikibase): Paper
- method description: CI findspot related from literature
- precision: ±0.0001°
- location type: Findspot
- point type: NotLur Place
- 1 reference

WKT Geometry

- Point(37.131 37.422)
- 0 references

Franchthi Cave modelled with fuzzy-sl as E53 Place

B5. FDOx 3DModel - Example CIIC 81 3D Model

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/cVOIH>

CIIC 81 - MD.cff

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/6VQJH>

CIIC 81 - CITATION.cff

4.1 Basic Metadata

```
# NOTE: FDOx uses https://schema.org/ (with s), not http://schema.org/
Q_BASIC = ""
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX schema: <https://schema.org/>
PREFIX fdo: <https://w3id.org/fdo-squirrel/>
PREFIX codemeta: <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>
```

```
SELECT ?property ?value
WHERE {
```

```
?fdo a dcat:Dataset .
VALUES ?prop {
  dct:title
  dct:description
  dct:created
  dct:modified
  dct:issued
  dct:hasVersion
  dct:type
  dct:license
  fdo:context
  schema:funding
  codemeta:programmingLanguage
  codemeta:codeRepository
}
?fdo ?prop ?val .
BIND(REPLACE(STR(?prop), "^.*/", "") AS ?property)
BIND(STR(?val) AS ?value)
}
```

| property | value |
|---------------|---|
| 0 context | Ogham Stones in the Wild and in Museums in Ire... |
| 1 created | 2024-06-05 |
| 2 description | good |
| 3 description | make 3d model available |
| 4 description | low |
| 5 description | Ogham Stone CO074-148---- located in the UCC S... |
| 6 funding | Community Project |
| 7 hasVersion | 1.0 |
| 8 issued | 2024-06-05 |
| 9 license | https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html |
| 10 modified | 2026-02-21 |
| 11 title | CO074-148---- |
| 12 type | http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147 |


```
display(Markdown("## 4.1 Basic Metadata"))
display(Markdown("***Software FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_sw, Q_BASIC)
display(Markdown("***3D Model FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_3d, Q_BASIC)
- = None # suppress Out[] cell output
```

4.4 Distributions / Files

```
# Distributions: FDOx uses fdo:sha256 (not spdx:checksum) and fdo:path
Q_DIST = ""
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
PREFIX fdo: <https://w3id.org/fdo-squirrel/>
```

```
SELECT ?path ?mediaType ?byteSize ?role ?sha256
WHERE {
  ?fdo a dcat:Dataset .
  ?fdo dcat:distribution ?dist .
  OPTIONAL { ?dist fdo:path ?path }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist dcat:mediaType ?mediaType }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist dcat:byteSize ?byteSize }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist fdo:role ?role }
  OPTIONAL { ?dist fdo:sha256 ?sha256 }
}
```

```
ORDER BY ?role ?path
LIMIT 30
----
```

```
display(Markdown("## 4.4 Distributions (first 30, ordered by role + path)"))
display(Markdown("***Software FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_sw, Q_DIST)
display(Markdown("***3D Model FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_3d, Q_DIST)
- = None # suppress Out[] cell output
```

| | path | mediaType | byteSize | role |
|----|---------------------------|--------------------------|-----------|---------------|
| 0 | fdo-metadata.ttl | application/octet-stream | 11096 | data |
| 1 | rdf_modelling_report.html | text/html | 17757 | data |
| 2 | CO074-148----.jpg | image/jpeg | 1311939 | documentation |
| 3 | Texture_Ortho.jpg | image/jpeg | 2307100 | documentation |
| 4 | rdf_modelling_report.json | application/json | 14611 | documentation |
| 5 | CITATION.eff | text/yaml | 326 | metadata |
| 6 | MD.eff | text/yaml | 2309 | metadata |
| 7 | CO074-148----.glb | model/gltf-binary | 126317064 | model |
| 8 | CO074-148----.nxs | application/octet-stream | 67575296 | model |
| 9 | CO074-148----.nmx | application/octet-stream | 15864576 | model |
| 10 | CO074-148----.ply | application/octet-stream | 84070110 | model |

4.6 Keywords / Subjects

```
# Keywords: FDOx uses both dcat:keyword and dct:subject (often duplicated)
# Mix of plain strings and Wikidata URIs
Q_KEYWORDS = ""
PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
```

```
SELECT DISTINCT ?keyword ?source
WHERE {
  ?fdo a dcat:Dataset .
  {
    ?fdo dcat:keyword ?keyword . BIND("dcat:keyword" AS ?source)
  } UNION {
    ?fdo dct:subject ?keyword . BIND("dct:subject" AS ?source)
  }
}
ORDER BY ?source ?keyword
----
```

```
display(Markdown("## 4.6 Keywords & Subjects"))
display(Markdown("***Software FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_sw, Q_KEYWORDS)
display(Markdown("***3D Model FDO***"))
sparql_table(g_3d, Q_KEYWORDS)
- = None # suppress Out[] cell output
```

| | keyword | source |
|---|---|--------------|
| 0 | Ogham Stone | dcat:keyword |
| 1 | UCC Stone Corridor | dcat:keyword |
| 2 | http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22731 | dct:subject |
| 3 | Ogham Stone | dct:subject |
| 4 | UCC Stone Corridor | dct:subject |

Query the FDO Metadata via SPARQL and Jupyter Notebook

Scientific

Crosswalking terminologies enable comparative research across datasets, regions, and research traditions.

Technical

Linked Data and RDF do not enforce a single model – they allow multiple models to coexist and be connected through mappings.

Infrastructure

Community knowledge graphs such as Wikidata and OpenStreetMap can act as hubs that connect heterogeneous archaeological datasets.

Scholarly

Mappings, alignments, and crosswalks are scholarly contributions – they formalise relationships between knowledge systems and knowledge graphs within the Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem.

Strategic

Interoperability is not a finished data model, but an ongoing process of alignment and integration.

Conclusion

Archaeological data will always be heterogeneous.

Linked Data connects models rather than replacing them.

Crosswalks and mappings are therefore core research infrastructure.

Community knowledge graphs can act as hubs for integration.

Interoperability is a process, not a final state.

To take home and discuss ...

Finis!

Thx!

Florian Thiery M.Sc.
Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA)
florian.thiery@leiza.de
ORCID: 0000-0002-3246-3531

NFDI4Objects

Community Cluster
**Semantic Modelling
& Linked Open Data**

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.19319520](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19319520)

